

analysis showed that photoperiod and temperature can affect fertility of PGMS protoplast clones.

Anatomical differences between and fertile periods in PGMS rice. The pollen sac and thrum (or filament) at the sterile stage were smaller than those at the fertile stage. Poorly developed vessel elements and sieve tubes of the anther vascular bundle and thrum vascular bundle (see figure) are abnormalities that can affect the transport of nutrients to the pollen sac, leading to microspore sterility.

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Attempted hybridization between *Oryza sativa* L. and *Porteresia coarctata* T.

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Wild halophytic *Porteresia coarctata* (2n=4x=48), endemic to the coastal areas in Bangladesh, is a potential source of salt tolerance for *Oryza sativa*. Crosses between these two genera were unsuccessful until Jena (1994) reported a hybrid between IR36 and *P. coarctata*. This triploid hybrid was much smaller than either parent and was completely male sterile. Sarker et al (1993) found that *P. coarctata* accepts *O. sativa* pollen readily, but not vice versa. Our crossing strategy therefore involved *P. coarctata*

(4x)/*O. sativa* (2n) and tetraploid *O. sativa* (4x-c)/*P. coarctata*.

Hand pollinations were made between the two genera. Gibberellic acid (75 ppm) with 0.1 % Tween was sprayed once 20 min after crossing. Embryos were rescued 10-12 d after pollination and cultured on 1/4 Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium with 0.45% agarose. Hybrids showing slow growth were kept on 1/4 MS for 8-10 wk. Plants were then transferred to the soil. Rapidly dividing root tips were stained with Feulgen.

Seed set percentage and survival among crosses were recorded (see table) The tetraploid hybrid from the cross BR-7 (4x-c)/*P. coarctata* grew vigorously and was taller than the induced tetraploid mother variety BR-7 (4x-c). Leaf texture was rough or intermediate between that of the parents. Leaves of the hybrid taper gradually compared with the abrupt taper of BR-7 (4x-c) leaves but not as gradually as those of *P. coarctata*. The hybrid did not set any seed on selfing. It has spikelets showing short awn and the curled morphology and asynchronized flowering pattern of *P. coarctata*. The hybrid from cross IR36/ *P. coarctata*, which showed parental isozyme bands both of *O. sativa* and *P. coarctata*, did not survive. The hybrid from BR-7(4x)/*P. coarctata* showed a faint band corresponding to that of *P. coarctata*.

Both *P. coarctata* and the tetraploid hybrid had 48 chromosomes. Chromo-

somes in the hybrid, counted from 50 cells, appear to be a mixture of the parents.

We examined 70 cells in triploid hybrids *P. coarctata* × Rajashail/Binnatoa and found them to have 36 chromosomes. The morphology of the triploid hybrid is close to that of *P. coarctata*. Three F₁s involving *P. coarctata* with Binnatoa 1, Rajashail 1, and Rajashail 4 showed 24.3, 15.3, and 30.8% seed set, respectively. Seed set in selfed *P. coarctata* was 94%. Embryos from three seeds obtained after back-crossing *P. coarctata*/Rajashail 4 with Rajashail pollen were rescued 11-13 d after anthesis and are currently being grown in 1/4 MS medium with 0.45% agarose.

Chromosomes of *P. coarctata* and *O. sativa* are small and not morphologically distinct from each other, making studies difficult on the tetraploid hybrid nature through standard karyotype analysis. We have multiplied the hybrid through vegetative propagation. We will examine it for hybridity based on meiotic chromosome and restriction fragment length polymorphism analysis.

Cited references

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Percent seed set and survival in crosses of *O. sativa* and *P. coarctata*.

Cross combination	Seed set (%) ^a	Germinated plants (no.)	Surviving plants (no.)
IR36 (4x)/ <i>P. coarctata</i>	1.6 (180)	3	0
IR64 (4x)/ <i>P. coarctata</i>	1.6 (120)	2	0
Latisail (4x)/ <i>P. coarctata</i>	0.16 (1250)	2	0
BR-7 (4x)/ <i>P. coarctata</i>	0.44 (900)	4	1
<i>P. coarctata</i> /Rajashail (2x)	2.34 (940)	22	4
<i>P. coarctata</i> /Binnatoa (2x)	4.16 (240)	10	4
<i>P. coarctata</i> /BR-7 (2x)	2 (1140)	6	0

^aValues in parentheses indicate total number of florets used in crossing.